

Appendix B: AI Act High-Risk Requirements Summary

This document summarizes the AIA high-risk requirements (Articles 8 to 17) and was provided to all respondents up to a week before the interviews. It is based on the final version of the AIA that was published in the Official Journal [1].

Risk & quality management system (Art 9 and 17)

- Foster adequate design & development of the system for the minimization of identified risks.
- Post-market monitoring system (details in Art 72):
 - Goal: continuous compliance with high-risk requirements.
 - Collect, document, and analyze performance data throughout the system’s lifetime.
- Testing procedures shall ensure:
 - Compliance with all requirements.
 - Consistent performance in line with the system’s intended purpose.
- Systematic documentation of techniques, procedures, and systematic actions for:
 - Design, design control, and design verification.
 - Development, quality control, and quality assurance.
 - Examination, test, and validation procedures.
 - Data management.

Data management & governance (Art 10)

- Quality criteria for training, validation, and testing data.
- Bias detection and mitigation.
- Consider the specific geographic, contextual, behavioral, and functional setting.
- Data gap and shortcomings identification.
- Data vetting for errors, as well as fostering relevancy, representativeness, and completeness of the data.

Accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity (Art 15)

- Goal: consistent performance throughout the lifecycle with appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity.
- Resilience against the exploitation of system vulnerabilities by unauthorized third parties that could influence the system's performance, outputs, or use in general.
- Types of attacks to be counteracted:
 - Data and model poisoning
 - Adversarial examples
 - Model evasion
 - Confidentiality attacks
 - Model flaws
- Technical & organizational measures against possible errors, faults, or inconsistencies.
- Robustness, e.g., through technical redundancy solutions like backups or fail-safe plans.
- Avoidance of negative feedback loops for continuous learning systems:
 - Mitigate possibly biased outputs influencing input for future operations.

Transparency and provision of information (Art 13)

- State the tested and validated level of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity.
- Users must reasonably understand the system's functioning and what data is processed.
- Appropriate interpretability of output for deployers.
- Technical capabilities and measures relevant to the explainability and interpretability of output
- Right to explanation of individual decision-making (under certain conditions):
 - Clear and meaningful explanations of:
 - * Role of the AI system in the decision-making procedure.
 - * Main elements of the decision taken.

Human oversight (Art 14)

- Appropriate human-machine interface tools for effective human oversight, proportionate to the risks involved.

Record-keeping (Art 12)

- Automatic recording of events (logs):
 - Ensure a level of traceability throughout the system’s lifetime.

Technical documentation (Art 11)

- Shall demonstrate that the system complies with all requirements.
- Including the system’s energy consumption and use of computational resources.
- A minimum documentation template is provided.

References

- [1] AI Act. Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence and Amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA Relevance), 2024.